

Formulation and Evaluation of a Herbal Lotion Incorporating Aloe Vera and Vitamin E

Shailee V. Tiwari*, Bhagyashri B. Sakhare*, Omkar A. Irlod, Avinash A. Kadam, Dhanshri S. Chatlewar, Rohan R. Ikkar, Sachin S. Narwade, Akash S. Mortate, Kunal D. Suryawanshi, Ramesh M. Bakan, Om S. Deshmukh, Shubham G. Kubade.

Shri Ramkrishna Paramhans College of Pharmacy, Hasnapur, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

*Corresponding Author mail ID: shailee2010@gmail.com

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KEYWORDS

Aloe-vera,
Herbal Lotion,
Herbal Cosmetic,
Herbal Formulation,
Wound Healing,
Skin Diseases,
Medicinal Plant,
Anti-inflammatory,
Pharmacological Properties.

ABSTRACT

The demand for herbal-based skincare products has surged due to their perceived safety and efficacy. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an herbal lotion incorporating natural ingredients known for their therapeutic properties. The primary constituents of the lotion include Aloe vera, and Vitamin E, which are renowned for their moisturizing, and antioxidant effects respectively. The formulation process involved the extraction of active components from these herbs, followed by their incorporation into a stable emulsion.

Various concentrations of the herbal extracts were tested to determine the optimal blend that provides maximum benefits without causing irritation. The lotion's physicochemical properties, such as pH, viscosity, and stability were assessed using standard methodologies. The evaluation phase included in vitro testing to ascertain the lotion's effectiveness and safety.

In conclusion, the formulated herbal lotion presents a viable alternative to conventional skincare products, offering a natural, effective, and safe option for enhancing skin health.

1. INTRODUCTION

An herbal lotion is a type of skin care product made using natural plant-based ingredients. These lotions are

often used to moisturize, soothe, or heal the skin without the use of synthetic chemicals. An herbal lotion is a moisturizer made from herbs and natural oils, often free

from parabens, synthetic fragrances, and artificial preservatives. These are used to treat dry skin, rashes, sunburn, or just to nourish the skin naturally [1,2].

Benefits of Herbal Lotion

- Gentle on sensitive skin.
- Fewer side effects compared to chemical lotions.
- Can be used daily.
- Eco-friendly and often cruelty-free.

The natural ingredients used by us in preparing the herbal lotion are Aloe Vera, and Vitamin E. Aloe is also common in both traditional Chinese and Ayurveda medicine. Aloe-vera has been used for centuries due to its healing properties, rich in vitamins, antioxidants, and amino acids. It helps to moisturize the skin deeply, alleviate sunburn, reduce inflammation and promote skin regeneration.

Vitamin E combined with other antioxidants have shown improvement in periorbital fine lines, roughness, radiance, skin tone, elasticity, density, collagen production and overall appearance of skin. A combination of the two herbs as opposed to individual herbs may offer a synergistic activity. This study is therefore designed to formulate a polyherbal face lotion that would serve as an antioxidant that will not only prevent the skin from the effects of reactive oxygen and free radicals but promote an overall healthy skin condition regardless of age [3, 4].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Aloe Vera leaves were procured from Sardespande nursery, Parbhani India. Other chemicals used in research were obtained from College Research Laboratory. All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

Method of formulation:

Collect raw material (aloe leaves) Washing leaf and removed base and tip of the leaf, leaf are cut into section (Filleting) Extract mucilage part of the leaves into mixing jar and Heat it and add agar agar into the mixing jar. Grinding/Homogenization of Unpasteurized Juice Add Vitamin E and Pasteurize the mixer cool the mixer of aloe leaf Packaged the produced gel and Stored it.

Steps Used in Formulation of Gel:

1. Reception of raw materials: The Aloe vera leaves after harvesting were preferably transported to the processing

place. The leaves should be sound, undamaged, mold/rot free and matured (3-4 years) in order to keep all the active ingredients in full concentration.

2. Filleting operation: It was shown that the aloe gel, once extracted from the leaf, had greater stability than the gel left in the leaf. In order to avoid the decomposition of the biological activity, the filleting operation must be completed within 36 hrs. Of harvesting the leaves.

3. Grinding/homogenization: The major steps in this process include crushing or grinding. The aloe gel fillets should be crushed and homogenized using a commercial high speed tissue crusher at room temperature (25°C). And add agar agar into the mixture.

4. Addition of vitamin E: The unpasteurized aloe gel juice was fortified with vitamin E to improve the flavor of Aloe vera gel juice and to stabilize the juice. It is used for its antioxidant activity

5. Pasteurization: Treatment (at 85-95°C for 1-2 min) is an effective method to avoid the bad flavor and the loss of biological activity of the Aloe vera gel.

6. Flash cooling: After pasteurization, the juice is flash cooled to 5°C or below within 10-15 sec. This is a crucial step to preserve biological activity of the Aloe vera gel.

7. Storage: Relative humidity and temperature are two most important environmental parameters that affect product quality.

Formulation of lotion

Beeswax and heated in a borosilicate glass breaker at maintaining the heating temperatures 75°C (oil phase).

In another beaker, we have dissolved borax, carbomer and vitamin E in distilled water by retaining temperatures 75°C of water bath. The solution was stirred with glass rod awaiting all solid particles get dissolve (Aqueous phase). Then gently we have added heated oily phase in heated aqueous phase with continue stirring process. After mixing both phases, immediately we have added aloe-vera gel, Coconuts oil with continuous stirring.

Creating a homemade aloe vera herbal lotion is a wonderful way to harness the plant's natural soothing and hydrating properties. Here's a simple formulation you can try.

Table 1. Formulation of Lotion

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Formulation A	Formulation B	Formulation C	Uses
1	Bess wax	2gm	3gm	4gm	Stabilizer
2	Coconut oil	3gm	4gm	5gm	Emollient
3	Aloe vera	0.59gm	0.60gm	0.61gm	Moisturizing Agent
4	Borax	0.1gm	0.2gm	0.3gm	To provide fine particles to polish.
5	Rosewater	3ml	4ml	4ml	Vehicle and soothing effect
6	Vitamin E	1 ml.	2 ml.	3 ml.	Antioxidant

Evaluation of lotion

The three formulations of lotion were subjected to various evaluation tests.

1. Organoleptic Test: The organoleptic test was observed visually by observing changes in smell, and color in the lotion preparations that had been made. Organoleptic testing aims to determine the organoleptic preparation which includes color and aroma according to the extract used (5).
2. Determination of pH: The pH of the lotion can be measured on a standard digital pH meter at room temperature by taking adequate amount of the formulation diluted with a suitable solvent in a suitable beaker (6).
3. Spreadability: The spreadability was expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from the lotion placed in between the slides, under certain load. Lesser the time taken for separation of the two slides better the spreadability. Two glass slides of standard dimension were taken. Then one slide of suitable dimension was taken and the lotion formulation was placed on that slide. Then the other slide was placed on top of the formulation. Then a weight or certain load was placed on the upper slide so that the lotion between the two slides was pressed uniformly to form a thin layer. Then the weight was removed and excess of formulation adhering to the slides was scrapped off. The upper slide was allowed to slip off freely by the force of the weight tied on it (7). The time taken by the upper

slide to slip off was noted. Spreadability can be expressed as,

$$S = m \cdot l / t$$

Where, m weight applied to upper slide.

l= length moved on the glass slide.

t= time taken.

4. Viscosity: Viscosity of formulated lotions can be determined by using Brookfield Viscometer (8).
5. Phase separation: Prepared lotion was kept in a closed container at room temperature, away from light. Then phase separation was checked for 24 h for 30 d. Any change in the phase separation was observed/checked (9).
6. Homogeneity: The formulation was tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch (10).
7. Removal: The ease of removal of the lotions applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap water (10).
8. After feel: Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amount of the lotion was checked and its phot is added below (10).
9. Skin sensitivity test (Draize test): A fixed amount of lotion was applied on intact skin of three human volunteers and left for 24h. The applied part of the skin was observed for any adverse reactions. Physical indications such as redness, inflammation, swelling, or a rash were observed for and noted (11).
10. Stability Study: The stability study at room temperature was determined for the period of 3 week. The tests were studied was color, sudden viscosity change, feel properties and emulsion stability (12-16).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The various quality control parameters Like Organoleptic Inspection, PH, Spread ability, Viscosity, After Feel, Phase Separation, Homogeneity, Skin sensitivity test, Irritancy, Washability, Greasiness, Stability and Antioxidant activity. Test. All parameter gives favourable result. The result obtained on present study shows that the active ingredients of these drugs when incorporated in Herbal lotion gives more stable products with good aesthetic appeal.

Evaluation Test

1. Organoleptic Test

The Formulation prepared was evaluated for the Colour, Odour and Consistency. The Colour of the lotion was observed by visual examination which is white in

Colour. The Odour of lotion was found to be pleasant. The State was lotion was examined visually. The lotion was semisolid in nature. The formulation was examined by rubbing lotion on hand manually. The lotion is having smooth Consistency. Results are listed in Table2.

Table 2 Organoleptic test results for lotion preparations

Formulas code	Color	Form	Smell	Texture
A	White	Semisolid	Pleasant	Smooth
B	White	Semisolid	Pleasant	Smooth
C	White	Semisolid	Pleasant	Smooth

2. Determination of pH:

The pH balance of the product is important as it affects skin and surface on which there are used. The pH of our Formulated lotion falls with the ideal pH range of the lotion. This ensure that the lotion maintain the skin natural pH .The results were shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Evaluation of pH

Formulas code	pH
A	5.06
B	3.99
C	4.38

3. Spreadability: Spreadability test aims to determine the area of the preparation that can be spread and evenly distributed when used. The spreadability result show that the F3 has the good spreadability among the formulation, making it easier to apply and more effective in covering larger areas with less product. The results are presented show in table 4.

Table 4 Spreadability observation table

Formulas code	Spreadability
A	spreadable
B	spreadable
C	Easily spreadable

4. Viscosity: The viscosity of a lotion is generally measured in centipoise (Cps) and falls within a range of 5,000-15,000 Cps, making it thinner than lotions which can be 15,000-50,000 Cps. Viscosity is a measure of how thick a liquid is, influencing factors like how easily it spreads on the skin and how quickly it absorbs.

Table 5 Viscosity observation table

Formulas code	Viscosity (Cps)
A	9944
B	9879
C	10918

5. Homogeneity Test: Based on the homogeneity test results , it shows that the four lotion formulas have a homogeneous composition and there are no coarse grains when the preparations are smeared on glass objects. This is in accordance with the requirements for homogeneity of the lotion, namely the lotion is said to be homogeneous if there is an even color equation and no particles are found in the lotion. This homogeneity test aims to see and know the mixing of the lotion preparation ingredients.

All the three formulas have shown homogeneity with no coarse particles in lotion.

6. Removal: Formulation A was found to not be washable easily, indicating it could not be removed without effort. Formulations B and C were easily washable, suggesting better user convenience and less likelihood of residue on the skin. This characteristic is important for daily-use products to ensure cleanliness and comfort.

7. Skin sensitivity test (Draize test): The results of the Draize test for sensitivity demonstrated that the three formulations were safe and skin irritation and allergic sensitization were absent. All formulations showed no redness, edema, inflammation and irritation during application as reported in table 6.

Table 6 Skin sensitivity test (Draize test)

Formulas code	Skin irritation	Redness	Inflammation
A	No	No	No
B	No	No	No
C	No	No	No

8. Stability Study: After 3 week stability study at room temperature all the lotion formulations were stable upto 2 week. Afterwards slight change in viscosity and feel was found with formulation A and B respectively. In 3rd week only formula C was found to be stable with white color, smooth feel and a very specific pH and viscosity. Hence, for the preparation of our herbal antioxidant lotion we considered formula C as optimized batch. The results of stability study are presented in detail in table 7.

Table 7 Stability Study of Base Formulation

Form ular code	Color	Sudden Viscosity Change	Feel	pH	Emulsion stability
		After 1 Week			
A	White	No change	Smooth	5.06	Emulsion Stable
B	White	No change	Smooth	3.99	Emulsion

					Stable
C	White	No change	Smooth	4.38	Emulsion Stable
		After 2 Weeks			
A	White	Slight change	Smooth	4.99	Emulsion Stable
B	Yellowish white	Slight change	Tacky	3.09	Emulsion breaks
C	White	No change	Smooth	4.30	Emulsion Stable
		After 3 Weeks			
A	Yellowish white	Change	Tacky	3.81	Emulsion breaks
B	Yellowish white	Change	Tacky	2.99	Emulsion breaks
C	White	No change	Smooth	4.30	Emulsion Stable

After the evaluation test study and stability study it was concluded that formula C was considered to be best for preparation of lotion.

4. CONCLUSION

Formulation and evaluation of herbal moisturising lotion by using herbal ingredient was successfully developed. Lotion formulation containing Aloe Vera and vitamin E were successfully prepared. The lotion's formulation with Aloe Vera helps to hydrate and nourish the skin, improving its elasticity and overall texture. Vitamin E further enhances moisturization and promotes skin repair. odour and semisolid state. Since the lotion was prepared by using simple ingredient and simple method so lotion is also economic. Evaluation test results of the Aloe Vera and vitamin E lotion have shown promising results. Formula C was seen to be stable over a three weeks period in stability study.

The outcomes of various lotion tests indicate that the Formula C formulation may be applied topically to moisturize and shield the skin from harm. Because natural medicines are thought to be safer and have less adverse effects than synthetic ones, they are more widely accepted.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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